

Calculating Breathing Rates from Remote PPG Signals Using Machine Learning Methods

Adara Andonie, Timothy Hanley, Dara Golden, Robyn Maxwell, Joe Lemley, and Ashkan Parsi

OCTO Sensing Team, Xperi Inc., Galway, Ireland

Abstract

Remote detection of health metrics, such as heart rates or breathing rates, has grown in interest. There is numerous amount of literature on calculating breathing rates using RGB cameras or thermal cameras but extracting the respiratory signal from NIR cameras is not straightforward. Thus, different ideas must be implemented. It is possible however to extract the PPG signal from an NIR camera, and from PPG signals breathing rates can be calculated. This research presents the first step in being able to predict the breathing rates from NIR cameras, which is to be able to predict the respiratory signal based on a remotely acquired PPG signal. Using machine learning, models were trained to predict respiratory signals from PPG signals. Results show that the models are predicting the respiratory signals with fair accuracy.

Keywords: NIR Cameras, PPG Signals, Breathing Rates, Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Breathing rate (BR) is an important aspect of health monitoring and can provide various information on an individual. The ability to accurately monitor health metrics remotely has many advantages in situations where devices cannot be used, for example, while driving, monitoring the elderly in their own homes [Aoki et al., 2001] [Martinez and Stiefelhgen., 2012] and monitoring infants [Scalise et al., 2011].

It is possible to obtain the BR indirectly through an ECG signal [Bao et al., 2020] [Kim et al., 2007], and less commonly done, the PPG signal as well. The PPG signal holds information for calculating health metrics, such as extracting the heart rate (HR) from the signal. However, the PPG signal contains information that makes it possible to calculate the BR from this signal [Karlen et al., 2013].

Often when remotely calculating BR, cameras such as RGB and thermal cameras are used. However, extracting the breathing rate from a Near-Infrared (NIR) camera is quite difficult as breathing is not so easily seen on these cameras which is why this paper is important because it provides a steppingstone in that direction.

Work combining machine learning to calculate the BR from health signals has been done [Ganser et al., 2019]. However, this research considered other metrics such as ECG, SpO₂, HR, and others from a device to predict the respiratory rate.

Currently, there is little literature on calculating the BR from only PPG signals and even less on predicting the BR from only the PPG signals obtained from NIR cameras. This paper will introduce a method to predict the respiratory rate based on remotely detected PPG signals from NIR cameras using machine learning, present current findings, and finally expand on future developments that can be employed.

2 Data Processing and Training Methods

This section will cover information on the data used for training, validation, and testing of the machine learning models, the data processing, and the background of the models used for training.

2.1 Materials and Data Processing

The training and validation dataset used is the BICMC dataset [Pimentel et al., 2017]. BICMC is a large public dataset, extracted from the MIMIC II dataset, containing signals (RESP, PLETH (PPG), V, AVR, II) and numeric (HR, PULSE, RESP, and SpO2). There was a total of 53 recordings done and each recording lasted 8 minutes. The signals were sampled at 125 Hz and the numeric were sampled at 1 Hz.

The data was downloaded and all the signals/numeric for each recording were combined into one large data frame for each recording. From these data frames, only the PPG signals, RESP signals, and times were extracted and then down-sampled to 30 Hz to match the sampling frequency of the test data, and the signals were then normalized between 0 and 1. These signals and times were saved as data frames for each recording. The data was then split 80% to training and 20% to validation.

The testing data was from the public dataset MR-NIRB [Nowara et al., 2022] which contains a series of videos of subjects in different driving scenarios filmed using both RGB and NIR cameras centered on the faces of the subjects. The subjects wore pulse ox to measure the PPG signal. From the NIR videos two PPG signals were considered for this paper: the ground truth PPG signal from the pulse ox and remotely estimated PPG signals calculated as a separate project.

Due to the lack of publicly available datasets containing both PPG signals and respiration signals, a different approach had to be taken to validate the results. As the PPG indicates HR, we have data with PPG signals in different HR ranges. For example, we have PPG signals that fall into the HR range of 50-60 beats per minute (bpm), 60-70 bpm, and 130-140 bpm. We validated the predicted signals with the idea that HR correlates with BR [Bahmed et al., 2016], as the lower the HR the lower the BR; the same applies for higher HR and higher BR. Thus, the number of peaks detected should correspond to the HR ranges.

2.2 Machine Learning Models

Several machine learning models for regression were used to predict the respiratory signal [Ganser et al., 2019]: OLS, Elastic Net, Bayesian Ridge, Lasso, Ridge, MLP, KNN, Random Forest Regressor, ADA Boost Regressor, and XGB Regressor. Out of these models, KNN and MLP proved the best for the task at hand. The qualifications that determined which models were better suited included the number of peaks of the actual respiratory signal and the number of peaks of the predicted respiratory signal from the test data and the clarity of the predicted signal. If a model had a poor signal, the peak detection would still consider weak points that would otherwise be invalid. This explains why even if the number of peaks for the actual respiration signal and predicted signal were the same, the model was disregarded.

Model	Actual Resp Signal Peaks	Predicted Resp Signal Peaks
OLS	17	17
Elastic Net	17	15
Bayesian Ridge	17	17
Lasso	17	15
Ridge	17	17
MLP	17	15
KNN	17	16
RFF	17	16
Ada	17	15
XGB	17	17

Table 1. Table comparing the results of the different machine learning models between the number of peaks in the ground truth respiration signal and the number of peaks in the predicted respiration signal.

3 Results and Discussion

This paper will focus on the results of the MLP model as an example. Figure 1 shows the non-filtered predicted respiration signal of the ground truth PPG signal with an HR of 50-60 bpm with a total number of peaks of 83. Figure 2 shows the non-filtered predicted respiration signal of the estimated PPG signal from a NIR camera with the same HR range of 50-60 bpm with a total number of peaks of 86. Figure 3 shows the non-filtered respiration signal of the ground PPG signal with a HR range of 120-130 bpm with a total number of peaks of 194 and Figure 4 is the non-filtered respiration signal from the estimated PPG signal in the same range of 120-130 bpm and a total number of peaks of 159.

Results demonstrate that the model can predict the respiration signal for various ranges of PPG signals. The number of peaks detected for an HR range of 120-130 bpm is 194 and more than halved (86) for an HR range of 50-60 bpm on the ground truth ppg signal. This pattern continues for the estimated PPG signal from the NIR camera. Another important detail to take notice of is the number of peaks from the ground truth signal prediction and its respective estimated PPG signal prediction. Even with no post-processing done, these numbers are relatively close to each other (83 and 86 number of peaks from lower HR and 194 and 159 for higher HR). These observations further indicate the accuracy of the model in the situation that there is currently no ground truth respiratory signal or BR to compare results due to the lack of available databases.

Figure 1. MLP Respiratory signal of ground truth PPG with HR range 50-60 bpm

Figure 2. MLP Respiratory signal of estimated PPG with HR range 50-60 bpm

Figure 3. MLP Respiratory signal of ground truth PPG with HR range 120-130 bpm

Figure 4. MLP Respiratory signal of estimated PPG with HR range 120-130 bpm

4 Conclusion and Future Work

Results from the machine learning models demonstrate that they can predict the respiratory signal based on provided PPG signals, with significant differences in the number of peaks for PPG signals with an HR range of 50-60 bpm and those within the range of 120-130 bpm for both the ground truth PPG signal and the remotely estimated PPG signal from a NIR camera. The next step in this research is to post-process the predicted signals in a way that doesn't overfit and skew the results such that the signals are clearer and easier to extract an accurate BR. Another important step would be to continue searching for available datasets with ground PPG and respiratory signals or start designing an experiment to collect the necessary information to test the training of the models more accurately. The exploration of different models will continue to be worth researching and trying. Deep Learning methods are currently being explored, such as LSTM and RNN models, to possibly improve the results of the machine learning counterparts.

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